

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING THE CONCEPT OF MASS IN 2ND GRADE

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Abstract

The article presents the content of the skills that are intended to be the subject of students in the process of teaching the concept of mass in the Measurements content line, which is included in the content of Mathematics in the second grades of secondary schools. The research presents the content of the psycho-didactic requirements that must be expected when forming concepts of measurement in the learning activities of students in general education schools. In general education schools, attention is paid to the presence of content elements that carry the "opportunity" function in the subject of mass on the "measurements" content line and the technology of their transformation into action in the students' cognition in order to directly connect the knowledge and skills they have acquired with life, to prepare them for the next stages of education by learning basic quantities, to develop students' spatial perceptions by getting acquainted with quantities, to learn to measure quantities, to acquire practical knowledge and habits necessary for life, to expand and deepen students' ideas about numbers and arithmetic operations by measuring quantities, etc. In the formation of these skills, attention is paid to the presence of content elements that carry the "opportunity" function in the subject of mass on the "measurements" content line and the technology of their transformation into action in the students' cognition. Based on these reasons, we conclude that the topic is relevant.

Keywords: methodological system, measurement, measurement skills, quantities, mass, methodology for teaching mass, conventional units of measurement, methodology for teaching kilograms, grams.

The actuality of the subject. The analysis of the materials obtained from scientific sources leads us to the conclusion that training is a way of implementing education, and the actual acquisition of moral knowledge, preservation of what has been acquired, and the acquisition of the experience of creative activity on its basis depend on the way of implementing education (the dialectics of the content and form of cognitive activity). The formation of a model of implementing education in didactics is an eternal problem.

Education of the present era, with its cognitive (perception) character, plays a greater role in the formation of a person as a creative personality. In modern times, to achieve success, it is not enough to just read, write, have knowledge of mathematics and natural sciences, but rather to demonstrate competencies. The development of information and communication technologies leads to an abundance of information in society, which requires the ability to learn independently. To survive and thrive in a rapidly changing, evolving world, modern youth need to develop skills such as decision-making, problem-solving, independent learning, collaboration, teamwork, evaluating different approaches, coming up with new ideas, taking initiative, and more. This creates conditions for sustainability for the future development of society. We know that the goal of mathematics lessons is not only to do calculations, but also to teach thinking, communication and problem solving. Preparing students for real life, creating thinking habits rather than memorization, and forming measurement skills to ensure integration with various subjects is very important in terms of improving calculation skills, in addition to daily needs. In the second grade, according to the content line of measurements, the skills of measuring length, mass, capacity, time quantities, as well as expressing them in different units are formed, they are introduced to new units of

length (meter, decimeter), as well as a new unit of mass (gram). General information about the calendar is given. They are taught to determine time more accurately in hours and minutes. However, there are some points that the teacher should pay attention to in the process of implementing what we have said: Students sometimes confuse the units of length meter and decimeter. Since the meter is used more in everyday life, it is appropriate to give priority to questions and tasks related to the meter. The section provides general introductory information about some concepts. Since superficial information about the calendar is provided, there is no need to explain the calendar in depth to students. The intended skills of students regarding the topic of time will be formed gradually, as they complete more practical tasks. Therefore, it is recommended that students ask more questions about the clock.

In today's society, where information and communication technologies are developing, the formation of skills such as using oral and written arguments convincingly in accordance with the context, and researching, collecting, and processing information should also be taken into account in the process of teaching quantities, and the development of mathematical language should be achieved. For this purpose, it is necessary to pay attention to the correct pronunciation when writing or pronouncing the appropriate units of quantities. Often, instead of "decimeter", it is pronounced as "desimeter". In this case, the teacher should make appropriate corrections.

Let's get acquainted with the methodology of teaching the concept of "Mass" in grade II. When planning a daily lesson, the first thing to do is to effectively determine the learning outcome of the lesson, which ensures the success of the lesson and the achievement of the set goal. When teaching the concept of mass, the

following learning outcomes are intended to be realized as an answer to the question "what will students learn":

- Calculates the total mass of objects based on the mass of one of the same objects, taking it as a constant;
- Calculates the mass of objects based on the weight stones given on the scale and compares them by weight;
- Measures mass on a balance scale using various conventional units of measurement (cube, ball, sphere, etc.);
- Uses grams and kilograms as units of mass;
- Finds the mass of the object in question by performing mathematical calculations using standard and non-standard units of measurement.

Considering that the effectiveness of visual aids in training depends on the correct selection of visual aids and the rules for their application in training, the use of lever scales, cubes, and various objects for measuring on scales prepared by students in the technology subject increases the effectiveness of training.

Students have been introduced to the concepts of "heavy" and "light" in grade 1. They already know that the most commonly used unit of mass in everyday life is the kilogram. This lesson explains that the mass of lighter objects is measured in grams, not kilograms.

The teacher gives the following problem:

– The candy is lighter than 1 kg. The brick is heavier than 1 kg. Which is heavier, the brick or the candy?

The main goal here is to make a connection between the students' existing knowledge and the learning outcomes of the lesson, to arouse their interest in the topic and to direct them to research. In other words, a bridge is created between the situation created through practical tasks and the concepts they will learn.

Mathematics consists not only of rules, symbols, pictures, diagrams, graphs and operations, but also of a system of order and relationships that form a whole. There are also relationships between mathematics and various sciences and disciplines. Situations created to apply the appropriate relationships serve to help students learn mathematics more deeply. During this organization of training, the knowledge and skills acquired are better remembered, the opportunity to assess the importance of mathematics in life arises, confidence in mathematical knowledge increases and students become interested in mathematics. Considering this, in order to ensure integration in the process of teaching the concept of mass, students can bring the balance scales they prepared from the technology lesson in the practical session to the math lesson.

Students will be introduced to various models of scales in this topic.

When talking about the mass of objects, it is necessary to form certain ideas about mass units in students. Which objects do we measure in kilograms and which in grams? To do this, it is necessary to show examples of objects whose masses are measured in kilograms and grams. The lightest objects are usually very light objects such as bird feathers, dandelions, feathers, thread, etc. The mass of these objects is measured in grams. It is not necessary for children at this age to accurately measure the mass of objects. By displaying objects in kilograms and grams in the classroom, you can form initial ideas about the difference between these mass units. In grade 2, addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division will be used when solving problems related to mass. Such problems serve to improve students' calculation skills.

To invite students to a discussion, a practical task can be given. The teacher draws a picture of a scale on the board and sticks words on sticky paper: orange - cherry, book - notebook, bread - bun, etc. Children should stick the paired words on the scales in such a way that the scale indicator does not change; for example:

Inquiry-based learning, which combines intellectual curiosity with learning, is a model of the scientific method adapted to the teaching process. It is an accepted fact that natural curiosity raises questions, and questions prompt us to seek answers, and this search leads to the acquisition of new knowledge and skills and thus to understanding the world. By involving students in such activities, it is possible to form skills such as goal setting, time and priori-test management, information processing, teamwork, written and oral communication, criticism, problem solving, and evaluation. For this purpose, after the above practical work is completed, the following research-discussion issue can be given:

– The mass of half an apple is equal to the mass of the small yellow cube. The mass of a whole apple is equal to 1 red cube. Then how many times heavier is the red cube than the yellow cube?

The task can be done practically both in pairs and with the whole class. Students can use the scales they prepared in the technology lesson. The main goal of the task is to find the mass of objects using conventional

units of measurement. Logical thinking is required to complete the task. There are several solutions to the given task: a) 5 small cubes; b) 2 large and 1 small

cube; c) 1 large and 3 small cubes. At the end, the ideas of students using different methods are discussed.

Then, the teacher summarizes the knowledge acquired by the students and directly presents the concepts, terms, and regularities implied in the learning outcomes. After the problem-centered activity, the use of concrete and descriptive models in accordance with the “concrete-descriptive-abstract” (CDE) approach during the explanation of the relevant topic has a positive impact on the quality of the learning process. In the process of learning new concepts (kilograms and grams), according to the “concrete-descriptive-abstract” approach, students should be given the opportunity to experiment with several models corresponding to the same concept. On the other hand, the “scaffolding” strategy aims to adapt the teaching process to the personal needs of students. Brief information about kilograms and grams is provided. Examples of objects

whose mass is measured in these units are shown. Several examples of scales explain why different scales are used.

It should also be noted that there is no need to teach that 1 kilogram is equal to 1000 grams in 2nd grade. Students will be introduced to numbers in the 1000 range in 3rd grade. It is enough to simply explain that very light objects are measured in grams.

After the explanation of the topic, examples and solutions (reinforced with pictures and models) that abstract the mathematical knowledge and skills that form the basis of the activity or topic explanation are given. At this stage, students are given the following task:

- Determine the masses of the objects on the scale:

Addition and multiplication skills are used to solve the problem. Students are expected to analyze these first (or listen to the teacher explain) and then explain it. The mass of the pose is appropriate. Then, similar tasks are provided for students to apply what they have learned.

After the mentioned stage is completed, it is the turn of the students. When shaping the learning activity of the students, a small number of tasks are presented that will allow the students to solve it freely and reinforce the relevant knowledge and skills that are intended to be acquired, considering the solution of the given task as an example. This will also help the teacher to conduct formative assessment.

Studies show that ensuring the success of learning is directly proportional to conscious assimilation. In other words, it is expected that students will master the knowledge so deeply that they will be able to apply the acquired knowledge in new concrete situations. The next stage of teaching the subject is the application of

the learned knowledge and skills to solving increasingly complex problems and modeling, which ensures the realization of the principle of conscious assimilation.

At this stage, it is appropriate to give the following question:

- A scale is shown in the picture. On one side of the scale are 2 boxes of tea and on the other side are 50 gram weights.

The question requires answering questions based on the picture.

- How many grams is 1 tea box? The mass of 1 tea box is found based on logical reasoning. There are 2 identical boxes in the left eye of the scale, and 2 identical weight stones in the right eye. If the mass of two identical boxes is equal to the mass of two identical weight stones, then the mass of 1 box is also equal to the mass of 1 weight stone. That is, 1 box = 50 g.

- What is the mass of 6 such tea boxes? It is considered 50-50:

In classes with technical capabilities, the problems in these sources can be solved: science-kids.co.nz/gamesactivities/math/measurements.html

In the further continuation of the educational process, the students' completion of the problem below has

a positive effect on their preparation, which, summarizing the obtained materials, leads us to the following conclusion:

- Lala weighed the tomato, pepper, and carrot separately on the scale. The tomato weighed 95 g. The pepper was 48 g lighter than the tomato. What was the mass of the pepper? The carrot was 25 g heavier than the pepper. What was the mass of the carrot?

When solving a problem, the teacher must ensure that students complete all the stages necessary for solving a problem - understanding, planning, solving, and checking. To do this, the teacher must ask guiding questions in accordance with the predetermined engagement stage and, if necessary, use visual aids.

In order to implement differentiation, which is an indicator of a teacher's competence and should be reflected in all his activities, there should be different approaches in this matter. It is advisable to implement this in two directions:

1) Support: Problems can be given on finding the mass of an object, knowing that the mass of an object is equal to the mass of several 2 or 3 kg weight stones.
2) Deepening: a) finding the mass of an object, knowing that the mass of an object is equal to the mass of various weight stones; b) problems can be given on finding the mass of an object, knowing that the mass of several identical objects is equal to the mass of several weight stones. Students can use the scale models they have prepared from life science.

A wonderful creative task can be given, such as "Measuring the mass of objects at home." In this way, students' understanding of mass and units, the method

of measurement, displaying data in a table, and comparing data are further strengthened. It is necessary to inform students that at home, with the participation of their parents, measure the mass of several foods used during the day on a kitchen scale. Determine which foods are used the most.

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